

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation**
of **Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

Deliverable Report

Document identifier: **DEL 6.1** Innovative technologies outlook update

Date Due to EC: **Month** M12 – 31st Oct 2017

Date of Delivery to EC: **31/10/2017**

Deliverable Title: Innovative technologies outlook update

Dissemination level: **PU**

Work Package: **WP6**

Lead Beneficiary: SAFT

Other beneficiaries involved: UNEW, UIC, UROS, STAV

Document Status: Final

Document Link: n/a

The OPEUS project consortium consists of:

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	Newcastle University	UNEW	UK
2	SAFT SAS	SAFT	FR
3	Union Internationale des Chemin de Fer	UIC	FR
4	Union Internationale des Transport Public	UITP	BE
5	Universitaet Rostock	UROS	DE
6	Stadler Rail Valencia SAU	STAV	ES

Document History:

Version	Date	Modification Reason	Modified by
1 st draft	27.09..2017	Initial draft compiled	SAFT
2 nd draft	23.10.2017	Update of model parameters according to power selected profile	SAFT
Final	31.10.2017	Document finalised for submission to the EC	UNEW

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WP6.1 of OPEUS project studies the critical innovative technologies for diesel hybrid rail vehicles. The deliverable consists of 2 chapters. The first chapter focuses on the state of the art of the innovative technologies for railway application such as DLC, Li-ion battery. The second chapter is aim to describe the characterization and identification of key parameters of ESS high performance batteries model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Railways have traditionally been regarded as an environmentally friendly form of transport. Based on previous successful international EU-Funded collaborative initiatives such as CleanER-D, OSIRIS, Roll2Rail, RailEnergy and MERLIN, OPEUS is aimed to develop a standardised simulation methodology for estimating, improving and optimizing the energy usage within rail system and particularly on in-vehicle innovation.

Figure 1. OPEUS WPs overview and interactions

Following the results of the SP7 simulation tools, the application of the innovative technologies (fuel cells, high performance batteries, double-layer capacitor and permanent magnet motors for electrical drives) should be analysed with respect to energy saving and life cycles costs for different traffic segments. According to the Technology readiness levels (TRL) described by NASA, OPEUS tool will build and expand these existing simulation tools from TRL3 (subsystem model are validated and realistic) to TRL5 (the enhanced new tool will be tested in a relevant environment using operational data and expected to meet the predicted performance). In OPEUS WP 6.2, thanks to the tool (developed in WP2, Figure 1), the four reference scenarios (described in WP3, Figure 1) will be used again to assess the potential of new ESS technologies such as high performance battery packs and the influence of introducing innovative ESSs in energy usage and overall cost. Before reaching the study of enhanced simulation tool, the OPEUS WP 6.1 focus on the critical innovative technology update applied in railway systems. It is essential to analyse the positive impact of such technologies on energy usage. The results of this WP6.1 shall allow having an update of outlook about the recent innovative technologies of ESSs, their integration into rail vehicles and also the more detailed description/characterization/identification of key parameters of ESS batteries.

2. STATE-OF-THE ART

Novel technologies and strategies are known to have a positive impact on energy usage particularly for urban operations where operational and topographic conditions favor these. Energy consumption in existing urban rail systems could be reduced by approximately 25-35% through the implementation of energy-optimized timetables from an energy-saving point of view, energy-efficient driving strategies improved control of comfort functions in vehicles and wayside energy storage devices (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2014a). The classification targets toward operational and technological measures which are developed in action matrix according to the rail system levels (rolling stock, infrastructure and whole system), Figure 2.

Figure 2. Main actions to save energy in urban rail (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2014a).

All the actions described in Figure 2 could be considered in five clusters:

- Recovering of regenerative braking energy and re-using it in electricity form through ESSs
- Enhancing of energy-efficient driving: by implying the eco-driving techniques and the optimized traffic management
- Enhancing of traction efficiency: contents the reducing energy losses in the power supply network, in on-board traction equipment and the reduction of vehicle mass
- Reducing the energy consumption of comfort functions (temperature control, ventilation, heating; air-conditioning, lighting, waste heat recovery,...) at different operation modes:
 - Service mode:
 - minimizing the heat transfer with outdoors (e.g.: thermal isolation materials, functionality of smart devices/components),
 - optimizing of the comfort temperatures adjustment
 - recovering the waste heat produced by the traction equipment
 - Parked mode: optimizing the setup and control of comfort functions (e.g. automatic heating/lighting control).

- Efficient measurement and smart management of energy flows
- The following table illustrates some of the potential gains that novel technologies and strategies could introduce:

Technology	Energy saving potential	Investment cost
Energy Storage Systems (ESSs)	5-25%	high
Eco-driving	5-10%	low
DAS	5-10%	medium
Lower resistance conductors	1-5%	high
Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSM)	5-10%	high
Software optimisation	1-5%	low
HVAC and lighting control in service	1-5%	low
HVAC and lighting control in parked mode	1-5%	low

Table 1. General evaluation of energy efficiency measures. (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2014a)

In order to minimize the energy consumption of urban rail system, a holistic approach, which bases on the energy consumption-related Key Performance Indicators (KPI), considers the numerous interdependences between subsystems such as vehicles, operations and infrastructure (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2015). The KPI in railway systems was been identified in the frame of EU-funded RailEnergy project. The Figure 3 show a set of combination of 10 KPIs and 12PI (Performance Indicators) for an investigation on the energy performance of a whole system and mains subsystems (or levels: supply network, rolling stock and infrastructure).

Figure 3. Structure of the proposed set of KEPIs

2.1. Regenerative braking

In the literature, with the aim of regenerating the braking energy, the four following methods are listed (Galaï-Dol et al., 2016) and illustrated in figure 4:

- Thermal traditional waste: before the development of power electronic (1970), the regenerative braking energy is transformed into heat thanks to the variable resistor banks
- Receptivity: the energy is used to directly feed in the railway network for the simultaneous use of other vehicles (starting-up vehicles)
- Back to the medium voltage electric grid through a reversible AC/DC
- Electrical storage: through the energy storage system (ESS)

Figure 4. Braking energy using (Galaï-Dol et al., 2016)

According to Galai-Dol's work, in the RATP (Parisian urban railway network), the receptivity of the braking energy sent to other vehicles can reach 96% (about 1.5MWh of usable energy with the current power electronics limitations).

Electrical traction is one of the new technologies and the most energy efficient traction system for reducing the energy consumption coming from traction requirement. One way to reduce the energy consumption in urban transit systems is to use the regenerative braking instead of pneumatic systems. The first example in OSIRIS WP3.1, the line 2 of metro in Rome could save 15% of energy traction consumption. The second one indicated that:

- the total energy consumption in Seoul urban rail systems could be reduced by 39% thanks to the regenerative braking
- the metro line in Milan could gain up to 44% of traction energy

Three last methods indicated by Galai-Dol can be considered into two kinds of use (Ghaviha et al., 2017):

- Simultaneous use: the regenerated energy feed simultaneously the power grid. However, the recovered power fraction is limited and might be turned into heat (which is dissipated to the environment) if there is no electrical energy consumption at the same time of regenerative braking. Another limit of power flow could come from the electronic controller associated to regenerative braking system (OSIRIS WP3.1) to avoid an overvoltage on the pantograph voltage. One solution might be useful to recycle such recovered electrical energy is to optimize the multiple trains in the railway network. However, the timetable optimization may limit the simultaneous acceleration of too many vehicles which could reduce maximum traction power, (Gonzalez-Gil et al. 2013).
- Later use: the recovered energy can be stored on stationary (electric railway infrastructure) or on-board in the train itself. Furthermore, the power and energy of stationary ESS require a more important capacity than the on-board ESS.

Several recent studies have success in recycling the regenerative braking energy with very high efficiency thanks to the dynamic models and the integrated optimization algorithms. Frilli et al. developed a Matlab-Simscape model combining the vehicle longitudinal dynamics and the electrical line in order to analyze the effect of stationary ESS or on-board ESS in the whole system (Frilli et al., 2016). The model was validated in case of Italian ETR 1000 train (Firenze-Roma

line). One third of regenerative braking energy could be recovered even when the braking frequency is quite low. Furthermore, the use of stationary ESS devices installed at electrical sub-stations could allow significant even in high-speed system.

Figure 5. Catenary of the Firenze-Roma high-speed line (Frilli et al., 2016)

Another use of braking energy is to combine its high regenerative braking frequency with low traction energy consumption in case of Beijing Yizhuang Metro line (Tian et al., 2016). Thanks to an energy optimization approach using Monte Carlo algorithm, the substation energy consumption can be reduced to 39% regarding the current automatic train operation of this Metro line. The usage of 96% electrical energy (recovered from braking phase) is the result of modifying the interstation travel time and parked time.

2.2. Onboard Energy Storage Systems

As described in section 2.1, one of the technological solutions to reduce the energy consumption, operating and maintenance costs of railway system is to regenerate the braking energy through the on-board ESS and reuse its electrical energy to feed the vehicles for multiple in-vehicle uses (e.g. in acceleration/deceleration mode, or during travel in catenary-free zones). The on-board ESS can also be recharged at passenger station. Three main elements commonly used in on-board ESS are flywheels (seldom), batteries and double layers capacitors (or supercapacitors). The two last will be considered in this work for further update of in-vehicle technology innovation. Their integration into hybrid or electrified vehicles plays the key role in terms of maximizing railway energy saving.

City	Operational	Length, Off Wire	Length, System	Supplier	Technology	Vehicles
Nice, France	2007	0.91 km total segments	8.7 km, 21 stops	Alstom	Battery, (Ni-MH) (SAFT)	20 CITADIS vehicles
Seville, Spain	2011	0.6 km line segment	2.2 km, 5 stops	CAF	ACR Evodrive supercapacitors	4 URBOS 3 vehicles
Shenyang, China	2013	Segments totaling 2.5 km	69.9 km, 65 stops, 4 lines	CNR Changchun	Voith supercapacitors	30 'dolphin' vehicles
Zaragoza, Spain	2013	2 km off-wire segment, charging at stops	12.8 km, 25 stops	CAF	ACR Freedrive battery / supercapacitors	21 URBOS 3 vehicles
Guangzhou, China	2014	Completely catenary free, charging at stops	7.7 km, 10 stops, Haizu Circle Line	CSR ZELC	SIEMENS SITRAS ES supercapacitors (Maxwell)	7 vehicles
Nanjing, China	2014	90% catenary free, OCS only at stops and acceleration points	8 km, 13 stops, Hexi line	CSR Puzhen	Bombardier Primove battery (Li-Ion)	15 FLEXITY 2 vehicles
Kaohsiung, Taiwan	2015	Completely catenary free, charging at stops	8.2 km, 14 stops	CAF	ACR Evodrive supercapacitors	9 URBOS vehicles
Dallas, TX	2015	Oak Cliff Streetcar, 1.6 km	2.6 km, 4 stops	Brookville	ABB battery (Li-Ion nickel manganese cobalt)	2 LIBERTY vehicles
Konya, Turkey	2015	1.8 km	21 km, 35 stops	Skoda	CATFREE battery (nano-lithium-titanium)	12 FORCITY CLASSIC 28T vehicles
Santos, Brazil	2106	0.4 km	11.4 km, 14 stops	Vossloh	ABB battery (Li-titanate)	22 TRAMLINK V4 vehicles
Seattle, WA	2016	Seattle First-Hill Streetcar, 4 km (downhill track)	4 km, 10 stops	Inekon	Battery (Li-Ion)(SAFT)	6 TRIO 12 vehicles
Detroit, MI	2016	New M-1 streetcar line, (length TBD - 60% of system proposed)	5.1 km, 20 stops	Brookville	ABB battery (Li-Ion nickel manganese cobalt)	6 LIBERTY 12 vehicles
Doha Education City, Qatar	2016	Completely catenary free, charging at stops	11.5 km, 25 stops	Siemens	SITRAS HES battery (Ni-MH) / supercapacitors	19 AVENIO vehicles
Granada, Spain	2017	4 segments totaling 4.95 km	15.9 km, 26 stops	CAF	ACR Freedrive battery / supercapacitors	13 URBOS 3 vehicles
Luxembourg	2020	3.6 km off-wire segment between Pont Rouge and Gare Centrale, charging at stops	16 km, 24 stops	CAF	ACR Freedrive battery / supercapacitors	21 URBOS 3 vehicles
Nice	2018	Completely catenary free, charging at stops	11.3 km	Alstom	SRS with Ecopack (battery / supercapacitors)	19 Citadis XO5 vehicles
Munich, Germany	201?	Planned English Garden extension, 1 km with 2 stops	8 km, 4 new stops	Stadler	Battery (Li-ion)	4 VARIOBAHN vehicles with batteries ordered (w/ 10 more pre-wired for future battery retrofit) All delivered, but only one vehicle currently fitted with batteries pending construction of new line.

Table 2. On-board ESS for off-wire LRV operation (Swanson et al., 2015).

An example of the hybridization of light rail vehicle (LRV) represented in the following figure, (Swanson et al., 2015). By the end of 2015, about nine systems using on-board ESS for off-wire operation and at least eight more under construction, Table 2.

2.2.1. Electric double layer capacitor (EDLC) technology

EDLC is also known as electrochemical double-layer capacitors which were originally named "supercapacitors" by Nippon Electric Company, or "ultracapacitors" by Pinnacle Research Institute. EDLC represent two main physics: energy storage in an electrochemical double-layer and the ions transfer as the results of electrochemical redox reactions.

Working as a power source, EDLC can ensure the storage of high electric energy amount in comparison the usual electrostatic and electrolytic capacitor. While having the similar chemical composition, the differences in term of capacity and of high durability (of EDLC) in charge/discharge cycles come from the conductive electrolyte salt in direct contact with the metal electrodes, the separator allowing the ions transport between the electrodes and the porous carbon with very high surface area electrodes .

EDLC becomes one of the most usable on-board ESS elements in rail vehicles with numerous advantages as below.

- Volumic capacitance of EDLC is about 10000 higher than the best regular capacitors.
- EDLC is capable to ensure the high current in charge even in short time. This pulse charge capability is currently suitable for braking energy saving and fast-charge stop.
- EDLC provide a high electrical efficiency: about 90%-98% (Borza 2017)
- Cycle life of EDLC is very long up to several million observed in laboratory even for deep discharge (>75% of stored energy), (Kurzweil et al., 2015). The lifetime decreases when the capacitance increases. The lifespan currently exceeds twenty years with one volt of supplied voltage drop. In traction applications, the lifetime of EDLC is predicted to be maximum about fifteen years with the end of life (EOL) criteria of 80% nominal capacitance or of 100% internal resistance (Meinert et al., 2015).
- EDLC can operate at a large temperature range (-50°C to 70°C) & voltage range (1-2.7V), (Borza 2017). Nevertheless, EDLC degrades quickly at high temperature. With acetonitrile electrolyte, the high performances are kept down to -40°C
- The power density of EDLC is considerably higher (1-20kW/kg) than the other on-board ESS, (Borza 2017). The peak power density can reach 50 kW/kg (in case of EDLC produced by APowerCap with activated carbon and no metal container), (Kurzweil et al., 2015):

Manufacturer	Technology	Voltage $U(V)$	Capacitance $C(F)$	Resistance $R(m\Omega)$	Energy Density ($Wh\ kg^{-1}$) for Discharge at $400\ W\ kg^{-1} - 50\% U_0$	Power Density ($kW\ kg^{-1}$)	
						95%	Peak
Maxwell (USA)	Activated carbon/ acetonitrile	2.7	<3000	0.38	4.2	0.99	8.8
Ness (Korea)	Activated carbon/ acetonitrile	2.7	1800	0.55	3.6	0.97	8.7
	Module: $18 \times 2000\ F$	48	111	4	3.9	1.3	–
Ioxus (USA)	Activated carbon	2.7	2000	0.54	4.0	0.92	8.2
Skeleton Tech. (Estonia)	Carbide carbon/ acetonitrile	3.4	<900	0.6	6.3	3.8	39
Panasonic (Japan)	Active carbon/PC	2.5	1200	1.0	2.3	0.51	4.6
	Active carbon/ acetonitrile	2.5	1791	0.30	3.4	1.89	17
			2500	0.43	3.7	1.04	9.2
Asahi Glass (Japan)	Active carbon/PC	2.7	1375	2.5	4.9	0.39	3.5
Nippon Chem-C	Active carbon/PC	2.5	2250	2.8	2.8	0.45	4.0
APowerCap	Activated carbon; no metal container	2.7	55	4	5.5	5.7	50
			590	0.9	5.0	2.6	23
BatScap	Activated carbon	2.5	2680	0.2	4.2	2.0	18
LS Cable	Activated carbon	2.8	3200	0.25	3.7	1.4	12
Hybrids							
Power Sys. Japan	Activated carbon/ graphitic carbon	2.7	1350	1.5	4.9	0.65	5.8
		3.3	1800	3.0	8.0	0.49	4.3
Yunasko (Ukraine)	Carbon, pouch cell	2.75	1275	0.11	4.5	8.8	78
	Carbon/lithium hybrid	2.7	5000	1.5	~20	3.4	17
Telcordia (USA)	Lithium titanate/ carbon hybrid	2.8	500	0.011	10	0.47	4.2
JSR (Belgium)	Activated carbon/ graphitic carbon, no metal container	3.8	2000	1.9	12	1.0	9.2
IMRA (USA)	Metal oxide hybrid	3.3	56	0.08	13	0.7	6.6

Figure 6. Performance data of selected supercapacitors (Kurzweil et al., 2015)

The specific power of EDLC provided is a factor of $U^2/4R$. An illustration of practical available power is given below:

Figure 7. Specific power of SC300F at ambient temperature (TA) over discharge time (Source: SAFT). ESR = Equivalent Series Resistance

One of the early integrations of UltraCaps into traction vehicles prototypes (Light Rail Vehicles (LRV), Metro-trains and Diesel Multiple Unit (DMU)) was realized by Bombardier Transportation in 2003 (Steiner et al., 2007). The experience on a prototype LRV equipped a MITRAC Energy Saver on-board gave about 30% traction energy saving. The similar effect of using an in-vehicle ESS was proved in Metro system. Concerning DMU, the application of on-board ESS leads to 25-40% decrease of energy costs and emissions.

According to further research, the use of carbon nanotube rather than porous carbon electrode in EDLC fabrication can lead to a specific energy of 85Wh/kg and about 3% loss of capacitance after 5000 redox cycles, (Lee et al., 2011).

Despite the advantages in term of power density, cyclability and wide temperature range, the supercapacitors also have the limits such as the moderate energy density and the high self-discharge.

2.2.2. Battery technology

Known as an ESU device thanks to high energy density and low self-discharge, a battery is considered a device which directly transforms the chemical energy inside the active materials to electric energy through a redox reaction between anode and cathode electrodes. The anode is always a reducing agent with high

coulombic (Ah/g), good conductivity, ease of production and low cost. The cathode uses an oxidizing agent (commonly metallic oxides) which is stable in electrolyte medium. The batteries are classified into two families: primary batteries (non-rechargeable) and secondary battery (rechargeable).

The first class of batteries are commonly used when the applications require a lightweight power source or a freedom of utility power such as utility metering, measure equipment, medical devices, military light system for soldiers, data loggers and a wide variety of other applications.

Figure 8. SAFT Lithium-Thionyl chloride-based LS, LSH cylindrical primary lithium cells with operating temperature of -60°C to 150°C. The main applications of LS33600 cells are utility metering, marine equipment, professional electronics and various other applications.

The energy densities of secondary batteries are generally lower than the ones of primary class, (Linden et al., 2001). Among the various technologies, Lithium is the best candidate providing the highest specific energy in the both primary and secondary classes.

Figure 9. Advances in battery performance for portable applications. (Linden et al., 2001)

As for the rechargeable batteries, their main applications are the storage of energy without being discarded. The following sub chapters will describe various rechargeable batteries depending up on technology.

2.2.2.1. Lead-Acid

Lead-acid battery was invented firstly by Raymond Gaston Planté in 1860. The batteries are made by lead electrodes and sulfuric acid-based electrolyte.

Figure 10. Lead-acid battery schematic diagram, (source: firstbatteryworld.com)

The major advantages of Lead-Acid batteries can be listed:

- Low-cost rechargeable batteries with local/worldwide capability of manufacturing
- A wide variety of size and designs: 1Ah to thousands Ah
- High power density which is attractive for engine starting in transportation

However, this technology gives a very limited energy density with a low cycle life, poor reliability, and shows significant performance decrease at extreme temperatures. Some types of characteristics and applications of Lead-Acid are shown in the following table, (Linden et al., 2001):

Type	Construction	Typical applications
SLI (starting, lighting, ignition)	Flat-pasted plates (option: maintenance-free construction)	Automotive, marine, aircraft, diesel engines in vehicles and for stationary power
Traction	Flat-pasted plates; tubular and gauntlet plates	Industrial trucks (material handling)
Vehicular propulsion	Flat-pasted plates; tubular and gauntlet plates; also composite construction	Electric vehicles, golf carts, hybrid vehicles, mine cars, personnel carriers
Submarine	Tubular plates; flat-pasted plates	Submarines
Stationary (including energy-storage types such as charge retention, solar photovoltaic, load leveling)	Planté;* Manchester;* tubular and gauntlet plates; flat-pasted plates; circular conical plates	Standby emergency power: telephone exchange, uninterruptible power systems (UPS), load leveling, signaling
Portable (see chap. 24)	Flat-pasted plates (gelled electrolyte, electrolyte absorbed in separator); spirally wound electrodes; tubular plates	Consumer and instrument applications: portable tools, appliances, lighting, emergency lighting, radio, TV, alarm systems

Table 3. Characteristic and application of various types of Lead-Acid batteries

(Linden et al., 2001)

2.2.2.2. *Nickel Cadmium (NiCd)*

NiCd battery use Nickel Oxide Hydroxide and metallic Cadmium as the electrodes. Despite of low energy density, higher cost than lead-acid batteries and the presence of Cadmium, they are very known for excellent reliability, long cycle life, high discharge rates, a wide temperature range (even in extreme temperature condition $\sim -50^{\circ}\text{C}$), good charge retention and capability of being stored for long period without deterioration. Furthermore, the NiCd batteries can provide a quasi-constant voltage over the whole State of Charge (SOC). There is no risk of battery sudden death. Possessing a low internal resistance, these batteries are capable to provide a very high power outputs in charge and discharge. The cost of maintenance is quite lower than other alkaline storage batteries.

Since the early years of the century, NiCd battery has been used extensively in traction application and particularly in railway. Up to the years of 2000s, about 40% of industrial NiCd batteries produced were used for in-train applications such as emergency, standby systems, lighting, emergency break, diesel-engine start-up, subway cars, and a wide variety of other in-vehicle applications as well as in rail station and traffic control systems. The higher energy density in term of weight and volume for rail market becomes more and more required. Particularly, when it comes from high-speed trains, mass-transit cars, subway cars and LRVs.

Figure 11. SAFT MRX Nickel-based battery system (30% lighter than std Ni-Cd batteries) integrated in Bombardier ALP-45DP dual-powered locomotive benefit from 60% weight saving in on-board batteries.

However, due to portable non refillable batteries, the image of NiCd battery is that it gradually loses its maximum energy capacity when the charge repeats after the partial discharge. The memory effect so-called lazy battery effect and the Cadmium presence are the main disadvantages of this technology. This effect is not seen on railway auxiliary backup application, where vented nickel-cadmium prismatic cells can be topped up with water.

2.2.2.3. Nickel Metal Hydride (NiMH)

Having the similar characteristics as NiCd battery, NiMH battery uses the Nickel Oxide Hydroxide for the positive and hydrogen-absorbing metal alloy for the negative electrode. Comparing to the NiCd battery, the energy density of metal hydride electrode is higher than the one of cadmium electrode which leads to the lower amount of the negative electrode and then higher capacity for NiMH battery. Since the last decades, NiMH rechargeable batteries have been widely used in various markets: industrial stationary, consumer electronics, power tools, electric/hybrid vehicles and particularly in railway applications despite the quick development of li-ion technology.

Figure 12. SAFT traction NiMH batteries (576V-80kWh) used in Nice Tram (France) with an operational life of at least five years. The benefits of using NiMH batteries are sufficient compactity to be installed into tram roofs and to minimize the engineering costs, (Sintropher 2015).

They still have the interesting advantages such as high peak power capabilities in charge/discharge up to 5C, low battery management complexity, slow irreversible aging at small depth of discharge (DoD) and low risk of serious hazards, (Pilatowicz et al., 2015).

Apart from the enormous advantages, NiMH battery still has a moderate memory effect, higher cost negative electrodes than NiCd battery. The discharge characteristic is flat with a low nominal voltage of 1.2V so that a lot of cell would have been connected in series to have a required high voltage for ESS applications. In addition, some NiMH battery can lose about 20-50% capacity (self-discharge rate = 50%-80%) after six months of storage (Energizer application Manual). This kind of battery suffers also a negative impact on lifetime due to the high power charge.

2.2.2.4. Lithium-ion

The Lithium metal is known thanks to good conductivity, light weight, high electrode potential for battery primary and secondary material. The high cell voltage results in significant energy density for Lithium batteries regarding the other high density traditional batteries (NiCd, NiMH). Over decades (since 1960s), the development of high-energy density Lithium batteries has required a lot of breakthrough technologies of new materials for electrodes and electrolyte.

The technology of Li-ion in the aim of energy storage, bases on the intercalation and de-intercalation of Lithium (Lithium cycle) between positive (cathode) / negative (anode) materials. The reversible electrochemical reactions take place at the active material particles surface, two flows of charges are created between negative and positive electrodes: the transport of Lithium ion into the electrolyte and the movement of electron through the external circuit (external load). Generally, the positive electrode material on an Aluminum collector is made from a compound of metal oxide and Lithium. The negative material is composed of Graphite on a copper collector. The electrolyte is finally a sort of Lithium salt. In 1990s, Li-ion batteries have been commercialized at large quantity production for portable devices market. Ever since, a numerous chemistry technologies have been studied and developed, make the li-ion battery more and more popular and competitive rather than other rechargeable batteries and ESS devices.

Regarding the traditional batteries, Li-ion battery shows some remarkable advantages:

- High energy density: the current range is approximately 80-300Wh/kg. Since the beginning, the energy density of Li-ion battery has steadily improved. In the period from 1996 to 1999, the specific energy of 18650 cell increased 8% per year. The other type 26650 cell reached 354Wh/kg (Linden et al., 2001). Recently, for the first time, an organic electrode-based Li-ion battery (with new carbon conductor and binder-free organic electrode) can achieve 470Wh/kg of energy density, (Kim et al., 2017). The following table qualitatively shows the energy density of various positive chemistry Li-ion batteries.

	NCA LiNiCoAlO ₂	SLFP LiFePO ₄	NMC LiNiMnCoO ₂	LTO Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂
Cell voltage, 100%/50% SOC	4.0 V/3.6 V	3.8 V/3.3 V	4.2 V/3.7 V	2.8 V/2.4 V
Energy	+++	++	+++	–
Power	+++	++	++	+
Calendar life	+++	++	+	–
Cycle life	++	++	++	+++
Safety	+	+++	+	+++
Cost	+	+	++	–

Table 4. Qualitative assessment of different positive electrode technologies, (Meinert et al., 2015)

- Moderate to high power density (0.25-1.3 kW/kg) thanks to several methods like decreasing the size of active material particles, modifying the

active surface of electrodes or synthesizing the new multi-composite of materials in particular of the positive electrode.

Due to the climate change and the clean environment policies, the EU countries have the agreements to cut their CO₂ emissions by 80% in 2050 and to less dependent from oil. Li-ion battery is considered as the very promising for the near future in transportation applications. In parallel of enormous advantage, the Li-ion batteries introduces some drawbacks such as the instability in abuse conditions (e.g overcharge, overheat). The following table illustrates a comparison of different chemistry technologies positive of Li-ion batteries in safety, (Andwari et al., 2017):

Technology	Advantages	Disadvantages
Lithium Cobalt Oxide (LiCoO ₂)	Power and energy density	Safety, cost
Nickel Cobalt and Aluminium (NCA)	Power and energy density, calendar and cycle life	Safety
Nickel Manganese Cobalt (NMC)	Power and energy density, Cycle and calendar life	Safety
Lithium Polymer (LiMnO ₄)	Power density	Calendar life
Lithium ion phosphate (LiFePO ₄)	Safety	Energy density, calendar life

Table 5. Safety comparison of different technologies of Li-ion batteries, (Andwari et al., 2017)

The LFP technology offers an inherent safety thanks to its thermal stability but low energy density compared to LCO types.

Figure 13. SAFT Xcelion 6T 24V 60Ah and 1.6kWh battery for military vehicles and industrial applications such as rail. The battery integrates the self shut-down in unsafe conditions.

However, LiFePO_4 has a lower working voltage ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ redox reaction 3.4V vs Li/Li^+) than other commercial layered materials. LiMnPO_4 is one of the good candidate for cathode material which have a high-voltage class (4.1V vs Li/Li^+). The poor Li^+ intercalation kinetics represented by the low conductivity of LiMnPO_4 than the one of LiFePO_4 can be enhanced by various synthetic methods to create the Nano sized $\text{LiMn}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{PO}_4$ powder (LMFP), (Kim et al., 2015). The LMFP would be useful for the applications that require slow discharge.

Figure 14. Voltage versus specific capacity of LFP cathode (left) and LMFP cathode (right)

More recently, using $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (LTO) instead of the graphite in anode (negative) electrode, the lithium titanate battery is a candidate for railway applications due to the various advantages regarding the current graphite Li-ion batteries, (Chauque et al., 2017) and (Nitta et al., 2015):

- High power performances at low temperature
- Long cycle life with a very small volume change in unit cell during the intercalation/de-intercalation (charge/discharge) phases: about 0.2% of change rather than 10% when using graphite anode material
- No film formation and growth of anode SEI
- Safety in term of thermal stability: thanks to the high potential of LTO, Lithium dendrite formation could be prevented even if the battery works at high rates.

However, the LTO battery has lower theoretical specific capacity than other anode technology batteries, as shown here-under:

Figure 15. Potential (vs Li/Li+) over specific capacity of different crystal structures

Figure 16. SAFT VL34570 LTO cell with very high energy density (160Wh/kg). The main applications of this LTO small cell are: mobile asset tracking, portable radios, soldier of the future equipment, electric bikes and personal mobility and numerous other applications.

LTO batteries have proven their success in power assist vehicular applications in the electrical buses. At each stop, the smart bus TOSA launched in 2013 (ABB 2013, Mwambeleko et al., 2017) can charge partly in a very short time of 15s the LTO batteries and then fully ultrafast-recharge it at the terminus line in 3-4 minutes.

Figure 17. TOSA bus equipped LTO batteries (ABB 2013)

In automotive application, the Skoda HP Perun bus has been recently equipped a 78 kWh LTO battery pack so that it can be fully recharged very quickly (5-8mins) and run 30km of road on a single charge (Skoda transportation 2016). The success of LTO battery in road applications (in this case the automotive one) give an interesting perspective for the rail applications because the rail transport consumes less energy per passenger kilometer than the road transport for the same traffic, (Mwambeleko et al., 2017). Furthermore, since 1975, the total energy

consumption for freight trains and passenger trains have been reduced by 46% per ton-kilometer and 62% per passenger-kilometer and the energy consumption of railway sectors shares only 2.1% of the total value of transport in general, (Ghaviha et al., 2017)

An overview of different Li-ion ion technologies in term of energy density and power density illustrates the switching between cell level and module level:

Technology		Elements	Modules
SAFT	Graphite-NCA	21.6 V / 42 Ah: 158 Wh/L	
Kokam	Graphite-LMO	25.9 V / 31 Ah: 152 Wh/L	
A123 Systems	Graphite-LFP	3.3 V / 20 Ah: 315 Wh/L	Not specified
Toshiba	LTO-LMO	12 V / 4 Ah: 63 Wh/L	

Table 6. Volumetric energy density at cell and modules levels of different Li-ion technologies, (Glaize et al., 2013)

Technology	Elements	Packs
SAFT Graphite-NCA Pulses of 18 s (element) and 30 s (pack) – (50% DOD)	21.6 V / 42 Ah: 533 W/kg 753 W/L	
Kokam Graphite-LMO Pulses at 3 C (element) and 10 C (pack)	25.9 V / 31 Ah: 991 W/kg 1517 W/L	
A123 Systems Graphite-LFP/ HPPC ²⁸ at 10 s (50 % SOC or DOD)	3.3 V / 20 Ah: 3000 W/kg 6760 W/L	Not specified
Toshiba LTO-LMO Pulses at 6 C (0.3 s)	12 V / 4 Ah: 300 W/kg 395 W/L	

Table 7. Volumic power density at cells and packs levels of different Li-ion technologies, (Glaize et al., 2013)

3. VOLTAGE BOUNDARY CONDITION OF BATTERY

The standard voltage of power supply from catenaries is 750V DC nominal. The maximum voltage is limited at 900V while the minimum voltage sets 500V, as per EN 50163 or prTS 50535. This means the limitations of battery voltage of ESS.

The following table describes some characteristics of sLFP (**Super Lithium Iron Phosphate**) VL30PFe Li-ion commercial batteries in SAFT:

Chemistry technology	Nominal voltage per cell	Standard voltage	Number of cells per module	Number of modules per box	Box nominal voltage
sLFP	3.3	750	12	20	792

Table 8. Configuration of one branch of sLFP Li-ion batteries (Source: SAFT).

With these specifications above, the total voltage of one sLFP box can be various between 600V min and 960V max.

4. DESCRIPTION AND IDENTIFICATION OF KEY PARAMETERS OF ESS BATTERIES

4.1.1. Description of battery model

In this section, the Li-ion batteries are considered for modelling as figure below:

Figure 18. Simple battery model

In figure, the battery is considered as an electrical circuit consisting of a constant voltage source (open circuit (OC) voltage or OCV) in series with a constant resistance that represents the ohmic voltage drop in the electrode, the electrolyte and the voltage drop due to the phenomena of charge transfer and transport of

material. The target of this section is to define the values to be applied for such a battery model to be applied in the global model in WP 3.

In this model, the open-circuit voltage V_{OCV} and the internal series resistance R_{series} are the functions of the state of discharge (or state of charge SOC). The terminal voltage of battery is calculated from the battery current I_{Bat} as follow:

$$V_{bat} = V_{OCV} - I_{Bat} \cdot R_{series} [Ohm]$$

Where,

- the open-circuit voltage can be obtained from the open circuit measurement
- the internal series resistance can be obtained from both the open circuit measurement and one extra measurement with load connected at the terminal. The sign convention of current, I_{Bat} : $I_{Bat} > 0$ in discharge, $I_{Bat} < 0$ in charge.

The state of charge for Ah can be obtained from the instantaneous current $I_{Bat}(t)$, the initial SOC_{init} and the nominal capacity:

$$SOC = SOC_{init} - \int \frac{I_{Bat}}{C_{nom}} dt [Ah]$$

The state of charge for Wh (SOC_e) can be obtained from the instantaneous current I_{Bat} , voltage V_{batt} and the initial SOC_{init} :

$$SOC_e = SOC_{e-init} - \int \frac{V_{batt} \cdot I_{Bat}}{Wh_{max}} dt [Wh]$$

In the model, an open-circuit voltage depending on the SOC (see table 13) will be used for the energy calculation. The remaining energy will be conforming to the IEC definition.

If the batteries pack has $n_{parallel}$ of branches in parallel and there is n_{series} cells in series. So, the branch resistance can be evaluated by:

$$R_{branch} = n_{serie} \cdot R_{cell} [Ohm]$$

And the equivalent resistance of the whole batteries pack is calculated following as:

$$R_{series} = \frac{R_{branch}}{n_{parallel}} [Ohm]$$

Where:

R_{cell} = internal series resistance of one cell

R_{branch} = total internal series resistance of one branch of nseries cells.

The total voltage of batteries pack can be represented as follow:

$$V_{bat} = n_{series} \cdot V_{cell} [V]$$

Values provided later on this DEL are concerning 1 branch later. The battery capacity, C_{bat} , can be obtained from each cell considering that all the elementary cells have the same characteristics:

$$C_{bat} = n_{parallel} \cdot C_{branch} [Ah]$$

As presented above, the simple model of battery bases on the branch internal resistance R_{branch} that can be evaluated from different tests of continuous charge/discharge following the calculus below:

in charge at 1C:

$$R_{ch} = \frac{V_{branch} - OCV_{branch}}{I_{charge}} [Ohm]$$

in discharge at 1C:

$$R_{dch} = \frac{OCV_{branch} - V_{branch}}{I_{discharge}} [Ohm]$$

The OCV curve in the following figure shows the cell voltage in open circuit as a function of state of charge (SOC).

Figure 19. Open-circuit voltage (OCV) vs SOC of single VL30PFe cell

At the end of life (EOL) of battery, the capacity and internal resistance of a single branch of 240 cells are defined as:

$$\text{Capacity (EOL)} = 0.6 \times \text{Capacity (BOL)}$$

$$\text{Cell resistance (EOL)} = 2 \times \text{Cell resistance (BOL)}$$

Furthermore, the resistance of battery (therefore including connections between cells and up to the external battery poles) in charge is different from the one in discharge at the same rate:

$$R_{\text{EOL-branch}}^{\text{dch}} = 0.652[\Omega] \text{ and } R_{\text{EOL-branch}}^{\text{ch}} = 0.648[\Omega]$$

It is therefore necessary to differentiate the resistances in the global model depending on current direction (positive current in discharge will provide traction assistance, negative current in charge will allow recovering energy from the train system).

4.1.2. Identification of key parameters of ESS batteries model

The basic case represents only the batteries pack depending on each specific application. One branch or one basic branch has 240 cells (20 modules of 12 sLFP cells) in series ($n_{\text{series}} = 240$).

The model should therefore be considering 240 cells as mentioned above (“one branch”). It is then possible to increase the ESS stored energy by paralleling such branches. A factor should be available for such purpose.

As a conclusion, all values are presented grouped in the following tables with: EOL_capa=-60% of initial Capacity and EOL_Resistance=+100% of initial Resistance:

EOL Internal resistance in discharge [Ω]	EOL Internal resistance in charge [Ω]	BOL capacity [Ah]	EOL capacity [Ah]
0.652	0.648	28	16.8

Table 9. EOL resistance of **single VL30PFfe branch** in charge/discharge and BOL/EOL capacity of **single VL30PFfe cell**

The **Table 10** supports OCV at different SOC for the simple model:

SOC [%]	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100
OCV [V]	600	758	769	775	779	782	787	790	790	790	790	791	794	799	800	800	800	801	825	881	912

Table 10. OCV table of single branch (240 VL30PFfe cells in serial per branch)

The conversion from Ah to Wh for VL30PFfe single branch is shown in the table here under:

SOC [%]	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100
Voltage for energy conversion [V]	600	745	757	764	770	774	778	781	782	782	782	783	786	791	792	791	791	792	816	870	912
EOL capacity [Ah]	0.0	0.8	1.7	2.5	3.3	4.2	5.0	5.8	6.7	7.5	8.3	9.2	10.0	10.8	11.7	12.5	13.3	14.2	15.0	15.8	16.7
EOL energy per branch [kWh]	0.0	0.6	1.3	1.9	2.6	3.2	3.9	4.6	5.2	5.9	6.5	7.2	7.9	8.6	9.2	9.9	10.5	11.2	12.2	13.8	15.2

Table 11. Energy conversion from Ah in Wh for different SOC of single branch (240 VL30PFfe cells in serial per branch)

Figure 20. ESS operating map (kWh) in continuous discharge at constant power over time.illustrates the characteristic of ESU operating map showing kWh curves over time for different constant power. The other Figure 21 shows the dependency of State of charge in term energy upon time. It can be noted that the values are provided per branch and that the time scale is very different from those of high power ESU (comparing 80 minutes discharge scale to a 300s discharge scale). This is perfectly normal as the ESU characteristics are very different for both cases.

Figure 20. ESS operating map (kWh) in continuous discharge at constant power over time.

Figure 21. ESS operating map (SOC_energy) in continuous discharge at constant power over time.

The Table 12 providing power prediction according to 3 given SOC 15%-50%-90% for one branch in both charge & discharge modes shall be used for the ESU model inside the vehicle model.

Constant Power prediction	SOC (%)	pp_ch5s (kW)	pp_dch5s (kW)	pp_ch10s (kW)	pp_dch10s (kW)	pp_ch20s (kW)	pp_dch20s (kW)
EOLch	90%	114	152	104	151	92	149
	50%	130	139	129	138	128	136
	15%	144	127	143	127	142	73
EOLdch	90%	81	154	81	152	57	150
	50%	129	140	128	139	127	137
	15%	143	128	142	127	141	120

Table 12. Constant peak power (in kW) prediction in charge/discharge for 3 given SOC.

The values in the yellow range correspond to a battery in charging mode, the values in the green range correspond to a battery in discharging mode, regardless the battery being charged or discharged in the following pulse (for which we are doing the power prediction). These estimations of constant powers should be considered as the input for driving strategy control of train.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The first chapter focuses on the state of the art of the braking energy saving and on-board energy storage systems of railway systems, in particular, the in-vehicles systems. About Li-ion batteries, the different technologies (including the new ones) applied for road and rail applications have been also updated.

In order to fulfil the OPEUS simulation presented in WP2 which model representatively a train including ESS systems, the second chapter is aim to describe the simple model and identification of key parameters of ESU high performance battery.

ANNEXES

TERMS AND DEFINITIONS:

- BOL: Begin Of Life, point at which the battery system has the rated capacity or energy fully available as minimum performance at manufacturer's delivery
- BMS: Battery Management System, system associated with a battery pack which monitors and/or manages its state, disconnect or isolate the battery pack, calculates secondary data, communicates data outside of the battery system and/or controls its environment to influence the battery's safety, performance and/or service life
- BTMS: Battery Thermal Management System, system associated with a battery pack which monitors and/or manages its thermal behaviour in order to maintain the temperature of the battery pack in the intended range for operational pattern agreed between the integrator and the battery system manufacturers
- ESS: Energy Storage System, physical system which consists of one or more ESUs and the other equipment required to connect to the DC link such as converters, control and monitoring systems, inductors, protection devices, cooling systems, etc
- ESU: Energy Storage Unit, physical equipment which is comprised of an energy storage technology, especially lithium-ion traction battery system in the context of this standard
- EOL: End Of Life, point at which the battery system cannot fulfil the required functionality or operational pattern as initially agreed among the user/ the integrator and the manufacturers
- KPI: Key Performance Indicators
- OCV: Open Circuit Voltage
- Lower limit discharging voltage of cell: lowest discharging voltage in the cell operating region from a safety stand point specified by the cell supplier
- Maximum voltage of the battery system: highest voltage of the battery system in which the maximum voltage of any individual cell is below the upper limit charging voltage of cell and any components operate in

- Nominal voltage: suitable approximate value of voltage used to designate or identify the voltage of a cell or battery system
- Rated capacity: capacity value of a cell or battery determined under specified conditions and declared by the manufacturer
- SEI: Solid Electrolyte Interphase
- Self-discharge: phenomenon by which a cell or battery system loses energy in other ways than by discharge into an external circuit
- SOC : State Of Charge. remaining capacity to be discharged, normally expressed as a percentage of full capacity by 303 selected expression as defined in Annex A of IEC 62864-1:2016
- SOE: State Of Energy
- Upper limit charging voltage of cell: highest charging voltage in the cell operating region from a safety stand point specified by the cell supplier

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